

Research

The Study on Impact Factors of Smartphone Addiction among Adolescence in Bangladesh

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Abstract: This study aimed to examine at Smartphone addiction characteristics, and also the predictive factors of the Smartphone addiction at school students in Bangladesh. This study explores the use and role of smart phones among adolescence in Bangladeshi school students. Four main categories are used to examine the students' mobile phone use: reasons to use mobile phones, model of mobile phone use, duration to use Smartphone, and psychometric behaviour-related issues. It is evident from this study that mobile phone effects on adolescence. The numbers of data for this study have been collected both from primary and secondary sources of information. A total of 1000 participants were preferred to complete a set of questionnaires, including the Smartphone Addiction Inventory Scale SPAI the in the Bengali and English language both. SPSS 22 was used to descriptive and factor analyses, t-tests and correlation analyses were conducted to verify the reliability and validity of the SPAI. Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($p < 0.001$), and the Kaiser-Mayer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy for the SPAI was 0.94, indicating meritoriously that the factor analysis was appropriate. The internal consistency and concurrent validity of the SPAI were verified (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.973$). There were 694 males and 306 females with ages ranging from 10 to 18 years old (M-16.2 Male, M-16.8 Female) included in this study. According to the Smartphone Addiction Proneness Scale scores, 296 (29.6%) were classified as a risk group for Smartphone addiction and 714 (71.4%) were recognized as a standard user group. The risk group for Smartphone addiction used a Smartphone for an average of 5 hour per day, which was 1 hour longer than that of the normal user group. This difference was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 14.017, p \leq 0.001$). The most frequently used SNSs were Facebook Messenger (10.4%) and Web media surfing 67.1% which is significant factor.

Keywords: Smartphone; School Student; Addiction; Adolescence; Bangladesh.

Introduction

Mobile phone usage so firmly integrated into young people's behavior that factors of behavioral addiction, such as Smartphone usage, interrupting their day-to-day activities. The main aim of this research is to investigate some elements of the emerging literature on the impact of mobile phones on adolescent life. The swift advancement in technology has completed many gadgets; a Smartphone is one of them [1]. People spend their time more likely on social media, do business emails, academic exploration, finding answers to questions, and playing games. Approximately 95 percent of Americans possess cell phones, and 77 percent possess Smartphone's. Worldwide, Smartphone's had used by 1.85 billion people in 2014, which had expected to be 2.32 billion in 2017 and 2.87 billion in 2020 [2]. Further, then 200 countries were anticipated to be using Smartphone's. "There are approximately 4.6 billion mobile phone subscriptions globally to which 11 to 12 million more than added every month(BMJ, 2006)". Mobile addiction has not only physical effects but also psychological and academics effects at the same time. Sleep deficit, anxiety, stress, and depression, all associated with internet abuse, have been related to mobile phone usage too [3]. All entities which can encourage a person can be an addiction. Whenever a habit has converted into an obligation, it becomes an addiction [4]. Few researchers believe that Smartphone usage and gender are not significantly associated [1].

According to Bangladesh Telecommunication Regulatory Commission (BTRC), the number of mobile phone subscriber is 158.438, the total number of internet subscribers 92.061 million at the end of February 2019, of which 86.268 million subscribers use mobile internet, WIMAX 0.061 million and other 5.731 subscribers ISP+ PSTN users (BTRC, 2019). More than 6.00 million new users added to existing Smartphone users (ERICSSON MOBILITY REPORT, 2015). In Bangladesh, mobile phone users are increasing rapidly, and a significant portion of the users are Smartphone users [5]. Among them, most of the users are young adults. The Smartphone is becoming more popular among the young generation, especially students. With the rapid growth of Smartphone users, the negative consequences of mobile phone users are increasing day by day. Usage of the mobile phone becomes one of the death causes when the victims walk and use a mobile phone on the rail tracks [6]. Mobile phone usage influences academic performance among secondary school students negatively impacts academic records [7].

This study aimed to examine factors to use Smartphone's, Smartphone addiction characteristics, and the predictive factors of Smartphone addiction in school students in Bangladesh, and it has initiated to determine the psychometric properties of the Smartphone Addiction Inventory Scale (SPAI). This study can distinguish Smartphone's and internet addiction among mixed Bangladeshi School students. Besides, the reliability and validity of the SPAI have also demonstrated. A total of 1000 participants were selected to complete a set of questionnaires, including the Smartphone Addiction Inventory Scale SAPI in the Bengali and English languages. This study flourished the first Smartphone addiction scale among Bangladeshi school students; Adolescence used mobile messengers for the longest, followed by Internet surfing, gaming, and social networking service used. There are the two groups showed significant differences in Smartphone use to the duration, awareness of game due to excess, and purposes of playing games. The predictive factors of Smartphone addiction have daily used Smartphone's and social networking service use duration, and the awareness of game overuse.

Literature Review

Smartphone Addiction

Smartphone addiction is measured to be rooted in Internet addiction due to the comparison of the symptoms and adverse effects on users. Smartphone addiction categorized as a behavioral addiction, such as Internet addiction. Behavioral and chemical addictions have seven core symptoms: salience, tolerance, mood modification, conflict, withdrawal, problems, and relapse [8, 9]. These common points have not integrally researched, but each symptom has found in Smartphone addiction studies. For instance, Lin et al. reported four features of Smartphone addiction, that is, impulse, efficient destruction, tolerance, and extraction. Bianchi and Phillips suggested that Smartphone overuse associated with psychological symptoms constitutes a form of behavioral addiction. Smartphone addiction is also considered a technological addiction that involves human-machine interaction [10].

A study reported that media addicts could not manage real-life activities [10, 11]. Adolescence utilizing the cell phone displayed more behavioral problems such as nervousness, temperament, mental distraction, and procrastination, and these problems worsened if the adolescences began using a cell phone at an early age [12].

The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of mental disorders (DSM-5, American Psychiatric Association (APA), 2013) introduced the diagnostic criteria for Internet gaming disorder. Oulasvirta et al. reported that the awareness of problems with repeated use of Smartphone's had underestimated, and only a few said that they were aware of it. The few respondents reported using a Smartphone as annoying, smart phone addicting, "a trap," and distracting. They have informed that repeated use could lead to addiction; however, they were unaware of the severity of the repeated and excessive use of a Smartphone. The awareness of the severity of Smartphone addiction can, therefore, play a role in preventing it.

Life satisfaction pertains to the rational evaluation of one's surroundings, and subjective happiness or personal contentment [13, 14]. Addiction to media could increase depressive symptoms and substance use, and decrease well-being [15, 16]. Samaha and Hawi showed that Smartphone addiction not directly linked to life satisfaction, but it has connected via perceived stress and academic performance.

Smartphone popular applications among adolescences in Bangladesh

Addiction varies according to the functions and applications to which the human being is addicted. Some recent studies have focused on addiction to particular Smartphone functions and applications, such as addiction to text-messaging [17, 18], addiction to SNs via Smartphone [19, 20], and addiction to WhatsApp [21], Face book, Imo, Messenger, TikTok, Video Games, YouTube, Viber so on.

According to Jafarkarimi, et al. [22] Face book has become the most popular social networking site with more than 2.2 billion users in the world wide. The satisfaction that Face book has brought has led to some addictive behavior among its users. Past Negative and Present defeatist orientations were positive predictors for both types of addiction, whereas Future time perspective was a negative predictor.

Likewise, WhatsApp and Messenger has become very popular application among young users. WhatsApp Messenger is a 'cross-platform messaging app which allows users to substitute messages without having to pay for SMS' (*WhatsApp.com, 2012*). The application is compatible with I-Phone, Samsung, Android, Nokia, and other Windows Smartphone's. WhatsApp features include one-on-one chat facilities, group chat, push notifications and sending and receiving both

video and audio files. On April 2014 it was estimated that WhatsApp had approximately 500 million users, who send and receive more than 64 billion messages a day (*WhatsApp.com, 2014*). In Bangladesh although numerous social apps (e.g., Face book, Twitter, Imo, WhatsApp and messenger) have been introduced, very few have been as widely received as WhatsApp. Interestingly, the focus group indicated that WhatsApp was the heaviest Smartphone's application use among adolescences. It highlighted five specific reasons for why teens heavily use What'sApp messenger, YouTube, Face book, Viber, Imo, Line as follows: (*WhatsApp.com, 2014*).

The simplicity of What's App messenger, YouTube, Face book, Viber, Imo, Line use, the low cost, its numerous positive uses, the program's good features, such as group chatting, sending photos, video, location, and contacts: finally, the possibility of broadcasting What's App messages to various contacts.

The results of the current study relate to the fact that messages can be tranquil and sent in a short time from virtually anywhere. Students prefer WhatsApp messages because the service is quick, cheap and convenient. They also use text messaging to coordinate with both friends and family [23].

The Influence Factors of Smartphone Addiction

Therefore, this research will divide the antecedents of Smartphone addiction among adolescences into Family variables, adolescences variables, Emotional variables, and technological variables and look at consequences that Smartphone addiction has on adolescence' mental and physical development.

Influence factors of Family

The closeness level within a family before students go to school will affect mobile phones' use to communicate with family. In a study of Japanese college students, Toda et al. [24] find an association between the level of care, essentially the closeness between parents and children, in a family and mobile phone dependence. Students from high care families are more likely to be dependent on a mobile phone than a low-care family. Interestingly, Toda et al. [24] also find a positive association between loneliness and high care families. This association suggests that those children from families characterized by high levels of involvement tend to

use technology, like mobile phones, to maintain that level of association with their families when they are away from home. This trend may indicate why family members separated by distance often use this technology to maintain communication with each other. Furthermore, the use technology to keep in touch with distant family members is an example of how families' structure influences the use of technology. It would be interesting to investigate other ways the structure and attitudes of families affect the use of technology.

One study finds that for teenagers still living at home, mobile phones function as a way to connect with family members when there are strained relationships within that family [25]. It is unknown how this relates to college students, as they are not under the direct control of parents while living away from home. It might be that the same type of communication with distant or estranged family members, such as a non-custodial parent, is more accessible in college since the student is out of the direct supervision of parents.

Need fulfillment is one of the main reasons college students stay connected to their families (Nasar, Hecht, and Wener; Sorokou and Weissbrod). Sorokou and Weissbrod[26, 27,] Show that a significant part of college students with family members is due to needing something, such as emotional or material support. Nasar, Hecht, and Wener [26] also find that college students use the phone for a feeling of safety and emergency contact in instances like a vehicle breakdown, along with an increase in risk-taking behaviors because of the perceived safety net offered by mobile phones. These findings are in contrast to studies indicating that younger children use the mobile phone as a way to coordinate family events and keep parents informed of the children's whereabouts (Devitt and Roker [25]; Palen and Hughes [28]. As school students are typically away from home, this day-to-day coordination of plans is unnecessary, meaning that school students likely use the technology differently than adolescences living at home. The primary use of mobile phone technology by school students is to satisfy students' practical needs rather than maintain strong familial bonds as seen with younger children. Technology does influence families in many ways, just as families or any other aspect of society influences technology.

In comparison, there are no studies directly showing the family influence on technology progression. It is a reasonable hypothesis that families can influence and adapt technology to

suit specific needs to avoid a simple technological determinism viewpoint; it is essential to understand how families can impact mobile phone technology. Since mobile phone technology is relatively new, its style and use are still in flux. Working from the SCOT co-construction of technology perspective from Oudshoorn and Pinch [29], how society influences how technology is adopted is as important as how technology impacts society.

Parenting Style

Types of parenting divided into authoritarian, permissive, and responsive [30]. Authoritarian is a one-way and rigorous way of raising children, strictly controlling their children. Permissive is full of affection, inconsistent, and laissez-faire. On the other hand, approachable is respecting children's autonomy, being reliable. Children from authoritarian parents lack their possess goals or judgments, exclusive and aggressive. Children from permissive parents are impulsive, selfish, stubborn, and hysteric. Children from responsive parents have clear goals and decisions of their own, self-regulated, and having high self-trust, they are likely to have positive and harmonious interpersonal relationships. Therefore, permissive parents are most likely to have children with a higher Smartphone addiction rate [31].

Besides, parents' attitudes towards Smartphone or usage behaviors are likely to have influenced children's Smartphone addiction rates the same as internet addiction of children [32]. When parents have more positive attitudes towards the Smartphone, they let their children use Smartphone more efficiently, resulting in a higher Smartphone addiction rate. Furthermore, if parents themselves are heavy users of Smartphone or addicted to it, their children have a higher chance of being exposed to Smartphone's, resulting in a higher Smartphone addiction rate.

Parent-Child Relation

One of the most general findings in studies of family and technology is that technology acts as a way for families to communicate and stay in touch. Communication technologies, like the internet and mobile phones, can serve as facilitators for extending family relationships across vast geographic distances [33, 34, and 35]. While this idea is not surprising by itself, the implications of technologies strengthening family bonds are interesting in light of popular

images of technology negatively influencing family life. The concept that technology can act to maintain or even enhance familial relationships separated by distance is crucial for this study. It also informs how a family member going to college can ease the transition toward becoming a full adult.

A common finding in several studies points to technology facilitating and extending communication within families. It appears to be especially prevalent in college-age people away from their families for the first time [34, 24]. The studies above show how widespread the internet and mobile phones are in maintaining family ties even across physical distances. Rather than being limited to the times when individuals are available near a landline phone, contemporary college students can interact with the family almost anywhere through mobile phones.

Due to the potential for more family communication, mobile phones can also act to ease the transition to adulthood. This concept points to mobile phone technology changing family life by extending the family into other aspects of social life and in the case of this study into school life. Rather than school functioning to separate the students from their families as they begin their adult lives. Some current research suggests that mobile phone technology permits children to stay within a dynamic family longer by relying on communication technology instead of self-reliance [36, 27]. Since the transition to adulthood in the age of mobile phone communications not very well represented in the literature, additional research needs to conduct to determine if mobile phone technology is influencing the transition process.

AdolescencesFactor

Adolescent variables affecting adolescences' Smartphone addiction are adolescence' age, gender, number of siblings, and whether they attend education institutions or not. The lower adolescent age is, mental development is incomplete and quickly immersed, having a higher possibility of Smartphone addiction [37]. Besides, boys tend to have more curiosity about tools and needs for trial. Also, boys tend to be more distractive and lack self-control [38], so they have a higher possibility of addiction to Smartphone's. While a higher number of siblings mean a higher probability of interacting with other people, a lower number of siblings

means more time alone, resulting in a higher possibility of addiction to digital tools like Smartphone's [39].

Besides, when a child attends education institutions like preschool or kindergarten, they are likely to be under the teacher's control. They have more time to interact with peers, resulting in lower Smartphone addiction rates. However, children not attending any education institutions have more time alone at home. Because of the lack of parents' resources, they have a higher possibility of Smartphone addiction. All focus group participants offered seven reasons behind Smartphone addiction among Adolescences in Bangladesh. Five of these reasons interrelated to students' Smartphone due to excess, while two reasons interrelated to Smartphone manufacturers. The ideas that interrelated to students integrated.

Technology Factors

Use Smartphone's to entertain them

In this study, concerning Smartphone addiction among adolescences, I think one of the reasons is the need for entertainment. Because of academic pressure, some students seek entertainment through listening to music or video games, whereas others prefer communication functions such as talking and texting".

Depending on certain Smartphone functions and Apps

Depending on certain Smartphone functions and Apps to accomplish their academic work, most students depend on Smartphone functions and applications to organize their daily work. But some students are addicted to using these devices because they rely on them too much; for example, they cannot finish their assignments without using their Smartphone's.

Excellence Through About New Devices and Apps before Others

Another reason behind the high percentage of addicted students was the desire for excellence among adolescences through experiencing new devices and applications before others, which makes them seek continually to discover more apps. Smartphone manufacturers gain benefits by attracting young customers by developing new applications that keep customers busy with activities to download and experience using the latest applications.

Social Network

Chatting via social media networking apps using Smartphone's is the easiest way to maintain friendships and increase social interactions. Despite that, some students talk online mainly to keep in contact with family members and friends. However, many students become addicted to chatting in a way that distracts them from their healthy life and affects their academic performance.

Likewise, the focus group participants existing two reasons connecting to Smartphone manufacturers: 1) Continuous upgrading of Smartphone devices, and 2) Attracting young consumers by developing new apps. Two of the participants clarified these reasons.

Continuous Upgrading of Smartphone Devices

The overall study focused that Smartphone manufacturers play an essential role in making people addicted to Smartphone use. For example, they continue to upgrade these devices and develop new functions and applications to increase their benefit, forcing them to change their devices regularly to follow these changes. As a result, the customers' usage rate continues to improve.

Research Methods

Participant

The sample has consisted of 1000 adolescents between 10 to 18 years of age ranges from Dhaka city. Dhaka is the capital city of Bangladesh, also known as a populated city in the world. Several secondary high schools were randomly selected and invited to participate in the study. Data were collected via surveys simultaneously completed by students in their regular used Smartphone's. Researchers and previously described a series of instructions about how to respond to the questions. They also emphasized the need for honesty when filling out the survey and guaranteed the confidentiality of the responses. All students have completed surveys consisting of various sections, the most prominent of which focused on the following:

a. Socio-demographic and academic characteristics, such as sex, age, current grade in school, grades repeated number of brothers and sisters, and monthly spend the amount of phone bill.

b. Basic parameters of mobile-phone use, including some calls, messages, and missed calls per day; the average amount of time spent using mobile phones per day (messages and calls); the monthly cost of mobile-phone use; ways of financing this cost; a form of payment (prepaid card or contract); hours of the day and place of most significant use and availability of the phone.

Measurement

This study aimed to develop a self-administered scale based on the distinctive features of Smartphone. The reliability and validity of the Smartphone's Addiction Inventory (SPAI) demonstrated. "The Smartphone Addiction Inventory (SPAI; Lin et al., 2014) was adopted to measure Smartphone addiction". This scale integrated 26 items that initially categorized into four dimensions: functional impairment (8 items), withdrawal (6 items), compulsive behavior (9 items), and tolerance (3 items). "Participants asked to rate these items on a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 4 (Strongly agree)". The SPAI displayed admirable consistency in the present sample (see the "Results" section for details).

The SPAI displayed admirable consistency in the present sample. A provisional scale was administered to several School students as a pilot study, testing the items for understandability and typographic errors and determining the duration of completion. This self-rating questionnaire contains 26 items. Sample items consist of "My recreational activities have reduced due to Smartphone use. "My family or friends complain that I use my Smartphone too much," and "I panic when I cannot use my Smartphone."

Method

All the data were analyzed using the SPSS 22.0 statistical program for Windows. Various Reliability analyses were performed. Descriptive and factor analyses, t-tests and correlation analyses were conducted to verify the reliability and validity of the SPAI. Basic and central-tendency descriptive statistics (Pearson vicariate correlations), and minimum significant differences (M/SD) will also be calculated.

Results and Discussions

Socio-demographic characteristics

The following are the results and findings obtained from primary data collected through questionnaires and interviews. The study findings show the percentage of male and female were 64.5% and 35.5% respectively. The result comes out of a significant deferent between male and female users. The class distribution were as in class 6-7 (6.0%), class 8-10 (31.6%), and class 11-12 (62.4%). It was found from the study that the majority (62.7 %) of the students were within 16-18 years of age, and 31.5% were within 13-15 years of age, and 5.8% were within 10-12 years average age 16.3(0.80). Family status; joint family from 32.2%, Single-family from 55.7% and single parent from 7.5% (The joint family is where living all family members like; parents with their child, uncle, and aunty with their child, Grandpa, Grandma. They cook together and eat together. Single-family is where living parents and their child, and a single parent is where living only a mother and her child or father and his child). Socio-economic status shows that high from 29.8%, Medium from 62.7%, and low economy from 7.5%. Table1. Describe that age 16-18, socio-economic statues medium and family single parents factors are significant shows negative correlations.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	645	64.5%
Female	355	35.5%
Age		
10-12	58	5.8%
13-15	315	31.5%
16-18	627	62.7%
Grade		
6-7	60	6.0%
8-10	316	31.6%
11-12	624	62.4%
Family		

Joint Family	322	32.2%
Single Family	557	55.7%
Single parent	121	12.1%

Socio-economic

Low	75	7.5%
Medium	627	62.7%
High	298	27.8%

Sibling

Below 2	392	39.2%
3-5	102	10.2%
Above 6	506	50.6%

Figure 1: Socio-demographic histogram.

Self Evaluation and Addiction characteristics

According to the table below, the average hours spent on common usage of Smartphone by the majority of the respondents (42%) spend time on 4 hours per working day and 66.6% spend time on the weekend, which is too much for students to spend those hours on social issues rather than academic issues which eventually affect academic performance. Because of the time needed by the student to concentrate on his/her studies, it almost occupied by social interactions like Facebook charting (uploading new images using her Smartphone), twitter, WhatsApp, and other social network sites. On a working day, 27.7% of students use their Smartphone's, which have mentioned addictive behavior. The information on table 3 below can also be present about the purpose of Smartphone use. Spend money per month average 58.4% are high range. The Smoking result comes out yes, 69.8% and 30.2% is no. The self-evaluation question remark addiction 17.1%, addiction 46.0% and don't know/ nothing 36.9%.). As for the usage of Smartphone's, the average hours were 3.03 during workdays and 4.07 during weekends. This result shows how higher learning students are addicted to using Smartphone's as some said that they could not afford to have it switched off because they have put their mind in waiting for the state to receive calls, messages, or even emails from their friends. So when they are in class, they put their Smartphone in vibration modes in the case will respond immediately when they receive either WhatsApp messages from their groups or elsewhere, so this makes them not concentrate on listening to the lecturers/instructors.

Table 2: Self Evaluation and Addiction Characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent	M	SD
Duration of working day			2.99	.952
2 hours	82	8.2%		
3 hours	184	18.4%		
4 hours	428	42.8%		
Above 5 hours	277	27.7%		
Less than 1 hours	29	2.9%		
Duration of weekend			3.50	.889

2 hours	51	5.1%		
3 hours	103	10.3%		
4 hours	166	16.6%		
Above 5 hours	666	66.6%		
Less than 1 hours	29	2.9%		
Spend Money			1.74	.587
200-400	342	34.2%		
Above 500	584	58.4%		
Less than 100	74	7.4%		
Self-Evaluation			2.20	.708
Addiction	171	17.1%		
Non-addiction	460	46.0%		
Don't know/Nothing	369	36.9%		
Smoking			1.30	.460
Yes	698	69.8%		
No	302	30.2%		

M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

Figure 2: Self Evaluation and Addiction Characteristics Histogram.

Purpose of using Smartphone

Data also represent that 67.1% of respondents said their Smartphone use purpose by surfing website and Media; 22.5% of respondents use their phone to Making Video and play Games. Very few, 10.4% respond to use Smartphone's during Messenger or SNS. For transactions, 80.0% of students use Smartphone's, and 20.0% can't make a transaction through the phone. Although for transaction Bangladeshi, people use the phone transaction app. The major part of the respond use Broadband Wi-Fi and use Android Smartphone, presentence of both results is 60.4%. 38.5% use mobile data and 1.1% percent use free Wi-Fi. I-phone users respond 32.9% and tab mobile users 6.7%.

Table 3: Purpose of using Smartphone

	Frequency	Percent	M	SD
Purpose			2.45	.835
Games and Making Video	225	22.5%		
Messenger and SNS	104	10.4%		
Web/Media surfing	671	67.1%		
Transaction			1.80	.400

Yes	800	80.0%		
No	200	20.0%		
Type of Smartphone			1.47	.619
Android	604	60.4%		
I-phone	329	32.9%		
Mobile tab	67	6.7%		
Type of Internet			1.79	.971
Broadband Wi-Fi	604	60.4%		
Free Wi-Fi	11	1.1%		
Mobile data	385	38.5%		

M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

Figure 3: Purpose of using Smartphone Histogram

Reliability and validity of SPAI among adolescences in Bangladesh

The questionnaire included a question about the self-perception of Smartphone addiction, which the participant evaluated from 1 to 10. The relationship between this answer to the question and the global scores obtained in the SPAI for constructed descriptive analysis. We also employed SPAI results according to participants’ age and gender for the criterion validity analysis, finding that both young people male and women achieved higher results on the SPAI scale. All participants in the study used Smartphone’s and the Internet in Smartphone’s, for example, they can log in to the social network. Thus, the tolerance should be reported by side information, such as item 1, “I was told more than once that I spent too much time on Smartphone.” However, as the second prevalent symptom in problematic cellular phone use in the previous epidemiological survey, “tolerance” could differentiate functional impairment caused by mobile phone use from those who had no functional impairment. The evidence suggested tolerance is a meaningful symptom. The descriptive statistics results show significantly correlated with the SPAI scale. The statistic sums up, and standard deviation shows the result is appropriate for analysis to accept 19, 22, 24, and 26 scores are little decreased. It demonstrated that compulsive Smartphone use could not be stopped even when the addictive individuals aware of the negative consequence. “Compulsive behavior” in SPAI included the items of the four factors, tolerance, withdrawal, compulsion, and interpersonal & health problems.

Table 4: Reliability and validity of SPAI among adolescences in Bangladesh

Reliability and validity of SPAI

	N	M	SD
SPAI 1	1000	3.374	.8769
SPAI 2	1000	3.378	.8342
SPAI 3	1000	3.394	.8303
SPAI 4	1000	3.361	.8541
SPAI 5	1000	3.348	.8495
SPAI 6	1000	3.382	.8323
SPAI 7	1000	3.332	.8869
SPAI 8	1000	3.385	.8219
SPAI 9	1000	3.373	.7991
SPAI 10	1000	3.335	.8874
SPAI 11	1000	3.347	.8422
SPAI 12	1000	3.345	.8501
SPAI13	1000	3.382	.8311
SPAI 14	1000	3.356	.8426
SPAI 15	1000	3.353	.8361
SPAI16	1000	3.376	.8120
SPAI 17	1000	3.365	.8767
SPAI 18	1000	3.318	.8635
SPAI 19	1000	3.388	.8533
SPAI 20	1000	3.339	.8780
SPAI 21	1000	3.429	.8171
SPAI 22	1000	3.468	.7386
SPAI 24	1000	3.444	.7909
SPAI 23	1000	3.379	.8124
SPAI 25	1000	3.410	.8189
SPAI 26	1000	3.620	.7377

Factor analysis for Smartphone Addiction Inventory (SPAI)

The value of 0.97 of Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin test of sampling adequacy and a significance of Bartlett’s test of sphericity ($p < 0.001$) indicated the suitability of (factor analysis) FA. The Cronbach’s alpha coefficient was 0.949 for the global inventory and 0.876, 0.888, 0.815, and 0.721 for each of the corresponding factors (compulsive behavior, functional impairment, abstinence, and tolerance) the results were very reliable. Table 5 shows the factor loadings results for each item. Which appropriately correlated with SPAI scale? The Cronbach’s alpha coefficient was 0.973 and the factor loads of compulsive behavior are 0.402** to 0.863**, functional impairment are 0.355** to 0.831**, Withdrawal are 0.414** to 0.812**, and Tolerance are loaded 0.352** to 0.868** ($p < 0.000$). The results of factor analysis are significant with SPAI main scale.

Table 5: Factor analysis for Smartphone Addiction Inventory (SPAI)

Item	Factor loading			
	Compulsive behavior	Functional impairment	Withdrawal	Tolerance
SPAI 7	.863			
SPAI 10	.601			
SPAI 20	.572			
SPAI 18	.521			
SPAI 6	.495			
SPAI 22	.446			
SPAI 5	.434			
SPAI 21	.519			
SPAI 11	.402			
SPAI 13		.831		
SPAI 26		.822		
SPAI 23		.767		
SPAI 8		.705		
SPAI 15		.545		

SPAI 12		.465		
SPAI 17		.464		
SPAI 24		.355		
SPAI 4			.812	
SPAI 2			.756	
SPAI 25			.752	
SPAI 14			.695	
SPAI 16			.574	
SPAI 19			.414	
SPAI 3				.868
SPAI 9				.855
SPAI 1				.352
Eigen	16.09	6.931	3.259	2.540
value				
Variance	34.251	9.749	7.187	4.427
(%)				

Person-Correlations, means, and standard deviations for the subscales of Smartphone Addiction Inventory (SPAI)

The present results also support the concurrent validity of the SPAI with four major psychological risk factors of Smartphone addiction. In the Person-Correlations analysis, the “Tolerance” factor obtained the lowest value (0.573**) with withdrawal, which decreases the score from the main score. Despite being the lowest one, it is a value that indicates acceptable internal consistency of the factor. Tolerance with functional impairment shows 0.568**, and tolerance with compulsive behaviors result shows 0.596**. Tolerance is a diagnostic criterion of any addictive behavior to substances. However, this dimension has questioned regarding the use of the Smartphone since its purpose is sometimes not voluntary but a consequence of the obligatory nature of specific circumstances such as work or family. One of the essential characteristics of SPAI is its four factors that emerge, since establishing similarities between addictions to substance and behavioral addictions. Their validity item ranges are(.302) and inter-

item correlated range (.404) indices significant result; it can distinguish addictive use by means of at least three decisive factors known to be involved in all addictive behavior: compulsive behavior, functional deterioration, and abstinence.

Table 6: Person-Correlations, means, and standard deviations for the subscales of Smartphone Addiction Inventory (SPAI)

	SPAI score	Compulsive behavior	Functional impairment	Withdrawal	Tolerance
Compulsive behavior	.878**	–			
Functional impairment	.888**	0.781**	–		
Withdrawal	.815**	0.673**	0.584**	–	
Tolerance	.721**	0.596**	0.568**	0.573**	–
Mean (SD)	3.38(16.77)	16.69(4.26)	14.77(4.31)	13.53(4.43)	6.57(4.22)

**p≤0.01.

SPAI scores between Risk group and Normal group.

A paired sample t-test and independent sample t-test has used to examine differences in the use duration of Smartphone, SNS, games, and messenger services between the two groups. To examine; whether these groups differed in terms of gender, age, parents style, family type, and socioeconomic status. The risk group for Smartphone addiction used 97.1% Of working day and 98.6% on working day. Smartphone use for an average of 5 hours per day, which was 2 hours longer than that of the normal user group. The risk group for Smartphone addiction used the mobile messenger, SNS, and Internet for significantly longer as compared with the normal user group. However, the normal user group played games for substantially longer than the risk group. Both groups' reliability Cronbach's alpha shows .988, which is a significant result.

Table 7: SPAI scores between Risk group and Normal group

	N	M	SD
Total score	1000	87.981	16.779
Risk group	296	28.451	6.71
Normal group	714	43.542	10.23

M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

Analysis of Impacted Factors among Adolescents Smartphone Addiction

Before analyzing the difference in Smartphone usage patterns between the two groups, we conducted a chi-square test to examine whether these groups differed in terms of gender, age, Family type, sibling (Table 8). There were significant differences in the demographic variables between the two groups. Both groups consisted of different magnitude of females and males. According to compare with Korean research (Smartphone use and Smartphone addiction in middle school students in Korea) we found that the risk group for Smartphone addiction spent more time on the Smartphone, mobile messenger, and SNSs than the normal user group did. Specifically, the risk group spent 5.2 hours while the normal user group 4.6 hours [183] reported that though Smartphone addicts used a Smartphone more frequently and for a shorter duration as compared with non-addicts, the sum of the duration of use in a day was longer for addicts as compared with that for non-addicts. The average age was 16.3 years in both groups, and 51.3 percent of them were from a single-parent family. Thus, the two groups showed a homogeneous composition. Out of 1000 participants, 605 (67.3%) were Male and 395 (32.7%) were Female, The chi-square result is $\chi^2 = 7.351^{**}$ which is significant with a male student. In a Socio-economic state, the higher was 333(28.7) medium was 559 (64.5%) and low was 118(6.8), chi-square is 1.013 is not highly significant with the result. As for family environments, 114(10.4%) students have single parents while 532(51.3%) students belong to single parents and significantly show the joint family 373(38.3), chi-square is $\chi^2 = 4.632^{**}$ which is a significant. The number of students who smoke was 341(31.6%) and non-smoke was 669(68.4) and chi-square is $\chi^2 = 157.573^{***}$ which is shown the negative behavior results. They were also not statistically significant, but they were significant than those who are smoking (see table 1). Based on the conducted research on 300 (55.6%) students, which was over 50%, the use of the messenger or

SNS was the major purpose of a Smartphone technology upgrade device, followed by 225 (22.5%) students who used them for entertainment purposes such as listening to music (see the table 2), watching movies, or playing games. In the self-assessment of Smartphone addiction, 171 (17.1%) students considered themselves as addicted to Smartphone, 460 (46.0%) students considered themselves as not addicted to Smartphone, and 369 (36.9%) and chi-square are $\chi^2 = 2.352^{**}$ students were unsure (See table 2). For the mobile transaction, the chi-square result shows $\chi^2 = 4.513^{**}$, and spend money on mobile use per month is $\chi^2 = 3.689^{**}$ which is indicates significant results.

Table 8: Demographic characteristics among two groups

Variables		Risk group for Smartphone addiction ($n = 296$)	Normal user group ($n = 714$)	Total ($n = 1000$)	χ^2
Sex	Male	185(65.5)	420 (64.8)	605(67.3)	7.351**
	Female	111(34.5)	294(35.2)	395(32.7)	
Socio-economic state	Low	43(4.2)	75(7.2)	118(6.8)	1.013
	Medium	152(61.3)	407(65.3)	559(64.5)	
	High	101(34.5)	232(27.5)	333(28.7)	
Family Statues	Joint	101(40,1)	272(33.7)	373(38.3)	4.632**
	Single parents	42(8.5)	72(9.1)	114(10.4)	
	Single family	153(61.4)	370(54.5)	532(51.3)	
Smoking	Yes	113(36.5)	228(29.3)	341(31.6)	157.573**
	No	183(63.5)	486(70.7)	669(68.4)	
Sibling	Less than 2	175(65.5)	252(33.7)	427(37.3)	.446
	3-5	101(20,1)	407(65.3)	508(52.7)	
	Above 6	45(14.4)	62(12)	107(12)	

Self-evaluation of Addiction	Non-addiction	98(31.9)	384(47.3)	482(35.7)	2.352**
	Addiction	56(19.1)	116(17.7)	172(18.1)	
	Don't know/Nothing	142(50)	214(35)	356(46.2)	
Mobile Transaction	Yes	201(80.2)	577(79.5)	778(79.1)	4.613**
	No	95(19.8)	137(20.5)	232(20.9)	
Spend Money for Mobile use	less than 100	12(2.1)	45(7.5)	57(4.2)	3.689**
	200-400	73(24.5)	257(33.3)	330(31.4)	
	Above 500	215(73.4)	412(59.2)	627(64.4)	

Frequency of Smartphone Addiction among Adolescents in Two Group

To measure the prevalence of Smartphone addiction in middle school students, we used a validated Smartphone Addiction Proneness Scale (Korean Information Society Agency, 2011). Sample items include “My homework dropped due to excessive Smartphone use,” “My family or friends complain that I use my Smartphone too much,” and “I panic when I cannot use my Smartphone.” The global Korean addiction score is risk group 40.48(4.2), normal group 30.62(5.3), and the total score is 33.67(6.7). Although the SPAI scale included 26 items that were originally categorized into four dimensions, so those totals score little increase. Risk group M (37.51), normal group M (31.76), is significantly high from normal group to risk group, total $t=41.11^{***}$. The SPAI displayed excellent reliability in the present result withdrawal $t=13.83^{***}$, tolerance $t=15.17^{***}$, positive anticipation $t=28.14^{***}$ and functional impairment $t=27.82^{***}$. All the t value shows a significant result.

Table 9: Frequency of Smartphone Addiction Among Adolescents in two Group

	Risk group for Smartphone addiction (n=296) 296(29.6%)	Normal user group (n=714) 714(71.4%)	Total (n=1000)	t
Smartphone addiction scale scores M(SD)	40.48 (4.2)	30.62 (5.3)	33.67 (6.7)	39.14***
Global				
Withdrawal	9.61(1.64)	7.61(1.07)	9.05(1.9)	13.83***
Tolerance	11.54(1.9)	8.13(1.9)	7.9(1.3)	15.17***
Positive anticipation	12.36(2.15)	6.01(0.9)	6.50(1.05)	28.14***
Functional impairment	5.20(1.7)	10.01(2.85)	12.7(2.87)	27.82***
Total Mean	37.51	31.76	36.15	41.11***

M= Mean ***p<0.001,SD= Stander Deviation

Daily use duration of Smartphone, mobile messengers, SNS, games, and Internet among two groups

The risk group for Smartphone addiction used a Smartphone for an average of 5 hours per day, which was 1 hour longer than that of the normal user group chi-square result $\chi^2 = 56.066^{**}$ and $\chi^2 = 14.017^{**}$ for both groups. This difference was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 14.017$, $p \leq 0.001$). Even regarding Smartphone use duration, excluding the time spent on calls and text messages, the risk group spent longer than the normal user group. The adolescences were using the mobile messenger for the most extended duration, followed by Internet surfing, game, and SNS. Surprisingly, they were using SNSs for the shortest term. The risk group for Smartphone addiction used the mobile messenger, SNS, and Internet for significantly longer as compared with the normal user group, chi-square is $\chi^2 = 31.8.5^{**}$ for both groups. However, the normal

user group played games substantially longer than the risk group (Table 10). The respondents were instructed to select two contents of a Smartphone and SNS that they used most frequently, and the two purposes of using SNSs. As evident from (Table 10)(61.1%) percent of the respondents used web surfing and instant mobile messenger contents the most, and more than(27.3%) percent of the respondents used music, games, and social networking. There was a clear difference between the two groups regarding the contents used.

Regarding the commonly used SNSs and the reasons for the same, there was no difference between the two groups. The most frequently used SNSs were Face book Messenger (10.4%) and Web media surfing 67.1%, which is a significant factor. There was a substantial difference between the two groups in terms of the awareness of their excessive game use ($\chi^2 = 12.07, p \leq .001$). The binary logistic regression analysis showed that the variables significantly related to the risk of Smartphone addiction were used 4 hours in a working day and 5 hours on a weekend of the average time. There is no significant relation with phone type and internet type with phone addiction; results come out $\chi^2 = 2.176^{**}$ for internet use and $\chi^2 = .336$ for the purpose of the phone.

Table 10: Daily Smartphone use of duration, mobile messengers, SNSs, games, and Internet among two groups

	Risk group for Smartphone addiction ($n = 296$)	Normal user group ($n = 714$)	Total ($n = 1000$)	χ^2
Phone type				.336
Smartphone	198(28.4)	488(62.3)	689(65.3)	
Others	98(10,9)	226(30.7)	324(32.7)	
Internet use				2.176**

Wi-Fi	179(23.3)	480(60.5)	659(55.9)	
Mobile Data	117(17.2)	234(32.5)	351(35.1)	
Purpose of Smartphone use				31.805**
SNS/ messenger	69(8.6)	79(9.9)	148(11.6)	
Games/ Making video	119(18.1)	234(32.5)	353(37.3)	
Web surfing/ Social media	108(16.8)	501(66.8)	609(51.1)	
Use of Working day				56.066**
Duration of Mobile phone use in working day (hour)	198(28.4)	459(53.2)	657(61.7)	14.017**
Use of weekend				
Duration of Mobile phone use in weekend day (hour)	245 (36.8)	512 (64.1)	757(70.4)	

Discussion

This study aimed to reveal the Smartphone usage pattern of addicted and non-addicted school students and identify the predictors of Smartphone addiction. Therefore, we examined the prevalence of Smartphone addiction, demographic characteristics, daily use duration of a Smartphone, commonly used content, and SNS, and game. To explore the risks and predictive factors of Smartphone addiction, we examined the physical and psychological health problems caused by Smartphone usage, the awareness of Smartphone addiction severity, and the effect of prevention education on Smartphone addiction. The prevalence of Smartphone addiction in Bangladeshi school students was 29.6 percent, which is a significant result of other countries' results. It is a very high rate compared with that reported in other countries. According to Article 30 of the act, all schools and public institutions obliged to carry out prevention education on Smartphone addiction.

However, this study examined factors of Smartphone use and Smartphone addiction within a relatively large convenience sample of young adults in Bangladesh. The study revealed four main findings:

1. The Chinese English version of the SPAI might provide an appropriate instrument for assessing Smartphone addiction in young people.
2. A longer duration of Smartphone use, and indicating that social networking is the most personally relevant factors of Smartphone function were positively associated with Smartphone addiction.
3. Smartphone addiction was more prevalent in adolescences (15–18 years), persons reporting lower physical activity, and those reporting higher stress.
4. Tobacco consumption was not related to Smartphone addiction.

The first analyses of the reliability and validity of the Chinese version of the SPAI showed excellent psychometric properties were verified with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.973. Although further validation is required, the results of the SPAI concerning the content validity of the scale were also promising regarding the association of specific indicators of Smartphone use (frequency, preferred Smartphone function) and Smartphone addiction factors (family, socio-economic status, social networking, etc.). Regarding Smartphone use, our multivariate analyses demonstrated that duration of use and time until working day and weekend provided better indicators for Smartphone addiction than use frequency. Mainly the factor of using Smartphone's

on workday and weekend indicates fun-seeking. It is in contrast to previous results showing Smartphone addiction to be more strongly associated with use frequency than duration [40,41].

However, in the present study, both use time and frequency were assessed using self-reports and may be biased due to recall-bias and time deformation. The higher prevalence of Smartphone addiction in a person's factor indicating social networking; as the most personally relevant function is in line with previous studies that showed that texting and the use of messengers and social media sites were predictors of mobile phone or Smartphone addiction factor [42,43]. The higher prevalence of Smartphone addiction in adolescents and those with both medium socio-economy and single-family factors indicates that targeted preventive measures should be considered, especially for these young people. Based on the results of [42] and, selective prevention efforts should also focus on groups with lower educational levels factor. Although the mutual influences of excessive Smartphone use factor, stress, and physical activity need further examination, the results of the present and existing studies showing associations between electronic media use at night and depression, and sleep disturbances [44] indicate that excessive Smartphone use factor might have adverse effects on several indicators of mental and physical health. However, the association between excessive Smartphone use and tobacco use obtained in either the present study or a current study conducted in Korea [42]. It is of particular interest factor, as studies on Internet addiction and alcohol problems revealed an association between the two domains [45, 46].

For instance, one of these studies reported that fun-seeking was the mutual characteristic of these two problem behaviors and might contribute to this relationship [46]. Future studies on Smartphone addiction, substance use, and associated personality characteristics factor might provide valuable insights into the mutual characteristics of different addictive factor disorders and reveal differences factor in the etiology of the Internet and Smartphone addiction.

It has been observed that 694 males and 306 females with ages ranging from 10 to 18years old (M-16.2 Male, M-16.8 Female) included in this study. According to the Smartphone Addiction Proneness Scale scores, 296 (29.6%) were classified as a risk group for Smartphone addiction, and 714 (71.4%) were identified as a normal user group. Descriptive and factor analyses, t-tests and correlation analyses were conducted to verify the SAPI's reliability and validity. Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($p < 0.001$), and the Kaiser-Mayer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy for the SPAI was 0.97, indicating meritoriously that the factor

analysis was appropriate. The internal consistency and concurrent validity of the SPAI were verified (Cronbach's alpha = 0.973).

This result indicated that the education factor was effective and that it needs to focus more on those at risk of developing Smartphone addiction rather than on normal users. Contrary to our study, Smartphone addiction was not related to gender, family income, or parents' education. These results are consistent with some studies that reported that Smartphone addiction is not significantly related to gender [47, 48, and 49,50]. In a study on cell phone usage of adolescences aged 10–18 years, neither household income nor parents' education was found to affect the use of Smartphone's [51]. As Smartphone's offer a variety of content customized to individual interests, every individual from different socio-economic factors backgrounds could find content that he or she is interested in or fulfills his or her need or deficiency. Thus, demographic variables showed no relationship with Smartphone addiction. The main purposes of using SNSs and games were fun, stress reduction, and communication with people. This result seems natural, but it should be interpreted by reflecting on the Bangladeshi society, which greatly emphasizes children's education. Adolescences in Bangladesh have been expected to exhibit good academic performance in a competitive social impression. They experience high levels of stress associated with academic performance [52]. Most of the adolescents, thus, spend their little free time on a Smartphone, because there are not many leisure activities to relieve stress and have fun. In this environment, promoting Smartphone use with the inability to control their Smartphone use despite negative consequences could lead to addiction. The high prevalence of Smartphone addiction in Bangladeshi adolescences should be interpreted considering the social environment. Contrary to our study, the two groups showed no differences in life and relationship satisfaction. Life satisfaction is partly related to social ties [53], and frequent social communication has found to exert a positive influence on life satisfaction [54]. Internet users have fewer face-to-face interactions like heavy television watchers do [55]. Smartphone addicts who spend a lot of time on their phones have forced to reduce their face-to-face contact time. Therefore, Smartphone addiction has considered being related to loneliness and shyness [56]. Specifically, the higher one scores on shyness and loneliness, the higher is the likelihood that one would be addicted to a Smartphone. In this sense, we hypothesized that the risk group for Smartphone addiction would have lower interpersonal and life satisfaction than the normal user group. However, the risk group merely showed a tendency to exhibit lower life satisfaction as compared with the normal

user group. Our result recommended that life and interpersonal satisfaction levels could not explain the addictive use of Smartphone's alone, [57] reported that Smartphone addiction has not directly linked to life satisfaction. Still, it is via apparent stress and academic performance. Satisfaction with life should be explained by many other factors such as family support, doing what they want to do, personality, positive thinking, and so on. Future studies should investigate the relationship of Smartphone addiction with life satisfaction and other related variables to identify the extent to which Smartphone addiction can be explained by life satisfaction and to reveal the path of the influence of life satisfaction on Smartphone addiction. However, the satisfaction of the online interpersonal relationships in the risk group for Smartphone addiction may have compensated low satisfaction with their offline interpersonal relationships. To further examine the relationship between interpersonal satisfaction and Smartphone addiction. Consistent with other studies [58, 59], we found that the risk group for Smartphone addiction spent more time on the Smartphone, mobile messenger, and SNSs than the normal user group did. Specifically, the risk group spent 5.2 hours while the normal user group 4.6 hours[60] reported that though Smartphone addicts used a Smartphone more frequently and for a shorter duration as compared with non-addicts, the sum of the duration of use in a day was longer for addicts as compared with that for non-addicts. Another study that analyzed a large data set on actual Smartphone usage revealed that the users typically spent almost 3 hours per day on the Smartphone, but the duration was less than 20minute at each instance of use [61].

This study also reported the differences in app usage duration. News apps were accessed most frequently in a day, whereas communication apps used throughout the day. Using a data set on Smartphone use, [62] showed that a risk group for Smartphone addiction spent more time on Smartphone use per day than the non-risk group, and their use was greater in the morning-evening. The usage sessions initiated by the push notifications were longer for the risk group, which demonstrated that notifications acted as external cues related to problematic usage patterns. Also, the risk group consumed significantly more online content that can provide instant gratification. The multiple linear regression analysis revealed that the daily use duration of a Smartphone and SNS, and the awareness of game overuse predicted Smartphone addiction. As expected, longer daily use duration of Smartphone's predicted higher scores on the Smartphone addiction scale, but the awareness of game overuse predicted lower scores on the Smartphone addiction scale. Surprisingly, the shorter daily use duration of SNS negatively

predicted Smartphone addiction, which was contrary to our hypothesis and other studies. [63] Found that, among school students, one of the predictors of Smart phone addiction was time spent on SNSs.

In a European cross-sectional study, [64] reported that daily use of a mobile phone, increased social networking, female gender, not necessarily monthly payment as a type of contract, online shopping, viewing TV shows, downloading related activities, and messaging and chatting predicted mobile phone dependence in young adults. However, the above studies focused on young adults, and we could not find any studies on SNS use duration in adolescences aged 13–15 years. That is, when adolescences use Smartphone's daily for a long duration, using SNS could protect them from Smartphone addiction by engaging in the use of mobile messengers or gaming apps. It seems that using SNS has a positive function in preventing Smartphone addition.

However, the study aimed to evaluate the psychometric properties of the SPAI in a sample of Bangladeshi adolescences. We found a satisfactory model fit for the original four-factor the SPAI model. However, the four-factor model deemed as more fitting for assessing Smartphone addiction based on four indices of model fit. Similar to previous validation of this model (Pavia et al., 2016), reliability is excellent for this SPAI model. The present results also support the concurrent validity of the SPAI with four major psychological risk factors of Smartphone addiction. Specifically, there are robust positive associations of SPAI with loneliness, social anxiety, depression, and impulsivity. The magnitude of these associations is comparable to previous empirical evidence [56, 65]. Besides, the analysis yielded distinct associations among SPAI subscales that were positively associated with both motor and intentional impulsivity.

However, two of the SPAI subscales were not directly associated with non-planning impulsivity. The existing results also corroborated with past findings regarding the three facets of impulsivity. The present analysis also demonstrates the convergent validity of SPAI by revealing its strong positive association with Internet addiction. However, this association's strength does not exceed the suggested criteria for conceptual overlap between the two constructs (Kline, 2005). The association obtained in our study is more reliable; than those derived from previous studies using other measures to examine the association between Smartphone addiction factor and Internet addiction. This discrepancy to prior findings may occur as the SPAI is developed based on a valid date measure of Internet addiction (i.e., the CIAS-R). In hence the items of these instruments may have comparable wordings. Based on the present study, it observed that Smartphone usage has significant influence factors on addiction among adolescences in Bangladesh.

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained in previous exploratory studies showed that the mobile phone is one of the technological tools more used by adolescences. Some of the adolescences show the main symptoms which characterized the dependence disorders, such as excessive use, problems with parents, difficulty in controlling the use, interference with other activities, expressive embarrassment when they cannot use the smart phone.

This paper shows an instrument built to evaluate the dependence factors of mobile in adolescences taking into account the DSM-IV criteria for dependence disorders. This problem is not only new but also on the rise. It is necessary to continue to study the conditions that foster this dependence factor, develop prevention and treatment programs, and make an available assessment and diagnostic instruments that enable effective intervention. We believe (and hope) that this implementation can be useful for researchers and therapists working with mobile-phone dependence.

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Supplement

English version of SPAI scale: Smartphone Addiction Inventory Scale

- 1) I was told more than once that I spent too much on a Smartphone.
- 2) I feel uneasy once I stop the Smartphone for a certain period of time.
- 3) I find that I have been looking on Smartphone's longer and longer.
- 4) I feel restless and irritable when the Smartphone is unavailable.
- 5) I feel very vigorous upon smart phone use regardless of the fatigues experienced.
- 6) I used a smart phone for a longer period of time and spend more money than I had intended.
- 7) Although using a Smartphone has brought negative effects on my interpersonal relationships, the amount of time spent on internment remains unreduced.
- 8) I have slept less than due to using the smart phone more than once.
- 9) I have increased substantial amount of time using smart phone per week in recent three months.
- 10) I feel distressed or down once I cease using smart phone for a certain period of time.

- 11) I fail to control the impulse to use a smart phone.
- 12) I find myself indulged on the Smartphone at the cost of hanging out with friends.
- 13) I feel aches and soreness in the back or eye discomforts due to excessive Smartphone use.
- 14) The idea of using smart phone comes as the first thought on my mind when weak up each morning.
- 15) To use a Smartphone has exercised certain negative effects on my school work or job performance.
- 16) I feel missing something after stopping the Smartphone for a certain period of time.
- 17) My interaction with my family members is decreased on account of Smartphone use.
- 18) My recreational activities are reduced due to Smartphone use.
- 19) I feel the urge to use my Smartphone again right after I stopped using it.
- 20) My life would be joyless hadn't there been a Smartphone.
- 21) Surfing the Smartphone has exercised negative effects on my physical health. For example,
- 22) Viewing Smartphone when crossing the street fumbling with one's Smartphone while driving or waiting and resulted in danger.
- 23) I try to spend less time on smart phone but the efforts were in vain.
- 24) I make it a habit to use a Smartphone and the sleep quality and total sleep time decreased.
- 25) I need to spend an increasing amount of time on the Smartphone to achieve the same satisfaction as before.
- 26) I feel tired in day time due to late-night use of the Smartphone.

About Author:

Jesmin Akter is a master's scholar of China University of Geosciences' China, School of Applied Psychology. Her academic background was BSc in Child development and family relation and MSc in Child development and social relation under the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. She was a specialist of pediatric therapist. Her passion will be a child Psychologist and researcher. Currently she is researching in "The Study on Impact Factors of Smartphone Addiction among Adolescence in Bangladesh". She has research interest in Developmental and educational Psychology and Applied Psychology associated field.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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